

Title: The Complete Parent Guide to Math Accommodations for Dyscalculia (K–12)

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Description:

This guide provides research-backed accommodations, advocacy scripts, and a full grade-banded breakdown of supports for students with dyscalculia and other math learning differences. It is free to share with credit under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license.

Contents:

- Printable PDF Guide
- IEP/504 Advocacy Tools
- Parent Planner and Grade-Level Recommendations